

Spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II) in water, soil and biological samples using heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones

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Abstract : Analytical applications of 2-acetylpyridine-4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (APMT) and 2-acetylfuran thiosemicarbazone (AFT) are reported for the first time. The reagents have been synthesized and characterized using IR and NMR spectral data. APMT and AFT have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II). The reagents give yellow colour with mercury(II) in sodium acetate-acetic acids buffers. Many cations and anions do not interfere in the determination of mercury. The methods were successfully applied to a number of water (potable and polluted), biological and soil samples containing mercury(II). The results of the proposed method in the analysis of samples are comparable with those obtained by dithizone method. The methods have high precision and accuracy ($s = 0.007$ and 0.018 for $4 \mu\text{g/mL}$ in APMT and AFT methods respectively).

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, mercury determination, heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones, environmental, biological and soil samples.

Introduction

Thiosemicarbazones are interesting analytical reagents¹⁻³. Although monothiosemicarbazones have been widely used for the spectrophotometric determination of metals ions, but heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones are not exploited much. The importance of mercury determination is well known. The analytical monitoring of mercury in environmental, biological, industrial and food samples is extremely important because of high toxicity of this metal both in inorganic and organic compounds. In continuation of our ongoing work on the analytical applications of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones^{4,5}, we report here the spectrophotometric determination of mercury in different aqueous samples.

This paper describes the non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II) as its APMT and AFT complexes in aqueous medium. A close literature survey reveals that APMT and AFT are so far not been employed for the spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II).

Results and discussion

The reagents (APMT and AFT), are easily obtained just as any monothiosemicarbazone. The reagents have been characterized using infrared and NMR spectral data. The infrared spectra of APMT and AFT showed bands

(cm^{-1}) at 3288(s), 3471(m); 3239(s), 3378(m,br); 3043(m), 3148(s); 1577(s), 1592(s); 1497(s), 1481(s); 1147(m), 1233(m) are respectively assigned to $\nu(\text{NH})$ asymmetric stretch, $\nu(\text{NH})$ symmetric stretch, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ aromatic stretch ($\text{sp}^2 \text{C}-\text{H}$), $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ Schiff's base, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ stretch of pyridine and furan ring and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibrations respectively. $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) showed signals at 2.39, 7.80; 2.27, 7.88 due to $-\text{CH}_3$, pyridine and $-\text{CH}_3$, furan protons of APMT and AFT respectively. Based on above spectral data, the structures of the reagents are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structures of heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones (APMT and AFT).

Table 1. Chromogenic characteristics of APMT and AFT

Metal ion	λ_{max} (nm)	pH range	Molar absorptivity ^a	Colour of the complex
Cu ^{II}	380	5-8	1.47×10^4	Yellow
Hg ^{II}	350	6-8	1.08×10^4	Greenish yellow
Co ^{II}	360	5-8	1.86×10^4	Orange yellow
Ni ^{II}	375	6-8	2.16×10^4	Yellow
Zn ^{II}	365	5-8	3.50×10^4	Pale yellow
V ^V	380	5-8	1.07×10^4	Yellow
Cd ^{II}	362	5-8	2.68×10^4	Greenish yellow
Cu ^{II}	380	6-8	3.33×10^4	Yellow
Hg ^{II}	350	6-8	1.92×10^4	Light Yellow

^aL mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Absorption spectra of 1×10^{-4} M solutions of APMT and AFT at different pH values were recorded and pK values were determined spectrophotometrically using Phillips and Merritt method⁶. The bathochromic shift of from 290 to 300 nm indicates that in solution on increasing pH, the >C=S group of reagent (APMT or AFT) is enolized and dissociated (Scheme 1). The values of deprotonation of APMT and AFT are 4.1, 3.1 (pK₁) and 8.2 and 6.4 (pK₂) respectively. The pK₁ and pK₂ values are presumably due to thione-thiol tautomerism and deprotonation of thiol (SH) group respectively.

Table 2. Physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of Hg^{II} complexes with APMT and AFT

Sl. no.	Characteristics	Hg(APMT) ₂	Hg(AFT) ₂
1.	λ_{max} (nm)	350	350
2.	pH-range (optimum)	6-8	6-8
3.	Mean absorbance	0.3803 ± 0.0003	0.4301 ± 0.0021
4.	Mole of reagent required per mole of metal ion for full color developed	15 Fold	10 Fold
5.	Time stability of the complex (in h)	6	12
6.	Beer's law validity range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.60 -16.05	0.80-8.02
7.	Molar absorptivity (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	1.08×10^4	1.92×10^4
8.	Specific absorptivity (ml g ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	0.054	0.096
9.	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^2$)	0.02	0.011
10.	Composition of complex as obtained Jobs and molar ratio methods (M : L)	1 : 2	1 : 2
11.	Stability constant of the complex	2.43×10^{11}	2.39×10^{12}
12.	Standard deviation in the determination of 4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of Hg ^{II}	0.007 ^a	0.018 ^b
13.	Relative standard deviation (RSD)%	0.086	0.44

Scheme 1. A general scheme showing enolization and deprotonation of thiol group.

A 0.01 M solution of reagents are stable for 12 h. The colour reactions of some important metal ions with the reagents are summarized in Table 1. In basic medium the ligands presumably exist in enolic form.

The colour reactions of reagents with mercury(II) are instantaneous at room temperature. The order of addition of metal ion, reagents and buffer has no effect on the absorbance of complexes. Various physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of the mercury complexes are summarized in Table 2. Stoichiometry of the complexes (M : L = 1 : 2) was determined by Job's continuous variation method and molar ratio method. Sodium acetate (0.2 M)-acetic acid (0.2 M) buffer (pH, 6.0, $\mu = 0.2$ and $T = 300$ K) and equimolar (2.4×10^{-5} M) solution of Hg^{II} and reagents were used in these studies. The dissociation constant (α) and concentration (c) of the reagent at intersecting point were used in the calculation of stability constant of the complex (see equation)

$$\text{Stability constant of } 1 : 2 \text{ (M : L) complex} = \frac{(1 - \alpha)}{4\alpha^3 c^2}$$

Table 3. Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of foreign ions in the determination of 4.0 ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) of mercury

Ion added	Tolerance limit		Ion added	Tolerance limit	
	AFT	APMT		AFT	APMT
Citrate	384	410	Mn ^{II}	110	150
Tartarate	296	296	Mg ^{II}	98	147
Urea	288	316	Pb ^{II}	42	42
Iodide	254	254	Cr ^{VI}	21	21
Bicarbonate	244	244	Zn ^{II} ^b	15	20
Thiocyanate	232	255	Cd ^{II} ^b	13	13
Sulphate	190	190	Co ^{II}	10	10
Oxalate	176	194	Ni ^{II}	9	9
Thiourea	152	152	Fe ^{II}	5	6
Nitrate	124	134	Fe ^{III} ^a	55	60
Acetate	118	118	Au ^{III}	4	4
Phosphate	120	125	Tl ^{III}	3	4
Bromide	116	160	Ag ^I	2	2
Chloride	70	120	V ^V	2	2
Fluoride	45	50	Cu ^{II} ^c	2	3

^aIn the presence of 40 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of fluoride. ^bIn the presence of 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of thiocyanate ^cIn the presence of 300 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of citrate.

Tolerance limits foreign ions : The effect of foreign ions which often accompany mercury has been studied by adding different amounts foreign ions to fixed amount of (8.02 and 4.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in APMT and AFT method respectively) of mercury(II) in solution. The colour reaction was studied as described in the standard procedure. An error of 2% in the absorbance of reaction mixture was considered tolerable. The results are given in Table 3. Larger amounts of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+} do not interfere in the presence of masking agents.

Applications : The present methods were successfully applied for the determination of mercury when present alone. The developed methods were also applied to the determination of mercury in water samples, biological samples and soil samples (Table 4). The results obtained in the analysis of different samples are comparable to the data obtained using dithizone method⁷. The present methods are simple, rapid and sensitive for non-extractive spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II) in aqueous medium.

Table 4. Determination of mercury in water, soil and biological samples

Name of the sample	Amount of mercury ^a found ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$)		
	APMT method	AFT method	Dithizone method
Drain water ^b	0.824	0.798	0.770
Lab water ^c	2.815	2.753	2.768
Sea water ^d	1.532	1.516	1.504
Tap water ^e	0.520	0.504	0.510
River water ^f	0.932	0.897	0.919
Road side soil	2.344	2.287	2.330
Urban soil	1.498	1.496	1.480
Agricultural soil	0.627	0.603	0.617
Brain damage patient	1.301	1.342	1.296
Kidney damage patient	1.328	1.366	1.314
Paralysis patient	2.185	2.224	2.209
Sheep liver	1.396	1.475	1.374
Fish liver	1.325	1.376	1.338

^aAverage of five determinations. ^bAnantapur town, drain water. ^cLaboratory water (Department of Chemistry, S. K. University, Anantapur). ^dBay of Bengal (Chennai). ^eAnantapur Municipal Storage tank water. ^fTungabhadra river water (Kurnool).

Experimental

Preparation of APMT : The reagent (APMT) was prepared by simple condensation of 1 mol of 2-acetylpyridine and 1 mol of 4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazide. In a 250 mL Erlenmeyer flask, a hot methanolic solution of 2-

acetyl pyridine (4 mL, 0.036 mol in 5 mL of methanol), 4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (3.75 g, 0.036 mol, dissolved in 10 mL of hot water) were taken. Suitable quantity (2 mL) of glacial acetic acid was added to the reaction mixture and refluxed for 3 h. On cooling the reaction mixture, light brown coloured product was separated out. It was collected by filtration, washed several times with hot water and 50% cold methanol. The compound was recrystallised from ethanol and dried *in vacuo*, yield 3.8 g, m.p. 183–185 °C.

Preparation of AFT : The reaction mixture containing 2-acetyl furan (4 mL, 0.0396 mol in 5 mL of methanol) and thiosemicarbazide (3.6 g, 0.398 mol dissolved in 10 mL of hot water) was refluxed for 4 h. On cooling a pale yellow coloured product was formed. It was collected by filtration, washed with hot water, cold methanol. The reagent was recrystallised from methanol and dried *in vacuo*, yield 3.5 g, m.p., 135–138 °C.

The reagent solutions (0.01 M) were prepared by dissolving 50 mg of the compound in dimethylformamide (DMF) in 25-mL standard flask. The reagent solutions were stable for at least 12 h.

Hydrochloric acid (1 M)-sodium acetate (1 M) (pH, 0.5–3.5); 0.2 M NaOAc-0.2 M AcOH (pH, 4–6) and 2 M NH_4Cl -2 M NH_4OH (pH, 7–10) solutions were used in the present study.

Stock solution (0.01 M) of mercury(II) was prepared by dissolving 0.27 g of mercuric chloride (Merck) in deionized water containing few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid and made up to the mark in a 100 mL volumetric flask. Aliquots of this solution were standardized⁸ with EDTA using Xylenol orange as an indicator. Dilute solutions were prepared from this stock solution. Solutions of large number of inorganic ions complexing agents were prepared from their AnalaR grade or equivalent grade water soluble salts.

Recommended procedure : An aliquot of the solution containing mercury in optimum concentration range (given in Table 2), 10 mL of buffer solution (pH, 6.0) and 1 mL of 0.01 M reagent solution were combined in 25-mL standard flask and resulting solution was diluted to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the solution was read at 350 nm against reagent blank. The measured absorbance was used to compute the amount of mercury from predetermined calibration plot.

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Instrumentation : Shimadzu 160 UV-Visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm (path length) quartz cell and Elico model LI-610 pH meter were used in the present study.

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